
Application of Statistical Process Control with Structured Equation Modelling of Health Care Improvement with the Pragmatic Paradigm

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Abstract

The application of Information Technology (IT) is aimed at delivering health care services by enhancing the quality of health services, reducing medical errors, and improving patient care. Mauritius have worked tremendously in promoting and enhancing their health care sector by adapting the recent and highly qualified systems and technologies in emergency health care services. The success, efficiency, and quality in health care today for countries and health care providers are measured through the systems and technologies that have been used to provide health care services. Likewise, this research aims to explore the use and extent of implementing IT services in the field of health care. The research is based on the pragmatism paradigm approach based on mixed methodology. This research contributes to the literature on Information Technology particularly in the field of health care. The results acquired from this research are found to be consistent with other researches, which highlighted the importance of advanced software and their significance in the health care organisations.

Key words: *Information Technology (IT), Pragmatism Paradigm, Emergency Health Care Services, structured Equation Modelling, Statistical process control.*

1. Introduction

World Health Assembly has indicated that almost every person needs to access health care services without any financial hardship. However, in some of the countries, the access to health care services is still unapproachable. The application of advance as well as efficient programmes based on information technology in the

field of health care has improved the access of health services [1]. Different applications and software have been introduced which assist in improving the quality of health services being provided in an organisation. Similarly, the “Statistical Process Control” (SPC) is a standard method used in the industry to measure as well as control the quality and efficacy of services for the users [2]. It helps in controlling and improving the manufacturing process to a greater extent [3]. This process enables the service provider to acquire quality data obtained in the real-time processing within a system [4]. Certain pre-determined control limits are plotted on the graph, which decrease the scrap and variability of the data.

The SPC is considered as a remarkable source in improving the productivity of a system, reducing the cost of procedure, and responding to the process change on a rapid basis [5]. It also helps in making the real-time decisions based on the ground evidences within the operational system.

The World Health Organisation (WHO) has ranked Mauritius at number 84 out of 191 nations regarding its quality of care services and efficiency of the healthcare administration system [5]. There is a wide range of public hospitals and clinics across Mauritius and other inexpensive private facilities, as well as state-run health care centres that provide free medical services to populations. It is essential to note that most health care providers, administrators and managers has received education locally although the modern equipment is deficient in many public institutions [6]. This lack of resource and channels for comprehensive communication and connection between various

fractions of current health care ensures long-term provision of services.

To evaluate the relation between process control and outcome variables, the Analysis of Moment Structure Programme is considered as one of the most comprehensively used programme for Structural Equation Modelling. This software is utilised in the research of organizational behaviour and management.

This research aims to measure the efficiency of health care administration of Mauritius using the mixed research methodology on the basis of analysis of Moment Structure Programme. The main aim of this research is to identify the shortcomings of the health care sector, demonstrate how the health care services of Mauritius could be improved based on the results obtained during this investigation. Another purpose of this study is to explore, identify, and describe the perceptions of today's health care executives, administration executives, health administration program managers, current roles and responsibilities of health administrators, related knowledge, skills, and experiences required to improve care quality. This information was used to build a theoretical model to answer the research question of what changes are needed in health administration program curriculum to develop the knowledge, skills, and experiences required to improve the quality of care. In the future, it is hoped that action research will be performed to identify specific changes needed in current health administration system to prepare future health administrators with the outcome competencies required to address the quality of care issues being identified today.

2. Research Questions

Below are the research questions of this study:

1. To what extent is the health care administration of Mauritius efficient?
2. Is the health care sector up to date regarding service provision?
3. How does a hospital's administration affect service delivery?

3. Literature Review

The quality of health care services provided to the service users has been measured largely in the existing literature [7]. The process of quality control in any organisational capacity is now based on the resources of information technology. For instance, SPC has been installed in many health care organisations, which is efficiently running the system with reduced cost. Therefore, it is confirmed that both the fields of health care and information technology are parallel to each other. It is becoming more apparent to both health care practitioners and administrative researchers that both fields have much to offer each other regarding quality

and cost management [6]. Clinical quality and process quality have both been found to be important in predicting patient satisfaction within the health care setting. Clinical quality has been identified to be primarily associated with practitioner performance, while process quality has been associated with administrator and staff performance. In this regard, Wiig et al. [8] instigated that the quantitative (cost saving) and qualitative (error reduction) quality measures of process quality have also been shown to be positively related to hospital employee commitment and control initiatives. The clinical quality has been defined as the quality of care as measured by information about the results of patient diagnosis and treatment (for instance, the length of stay, infection rates) [7]. This definition provides focus on best medical practices relating to patient diagnosis. For this study, clinical quality relates to the degree to which health care practitioners follow best medical practices in treating and diagnosing their patients. Another common definition of health care quality relates to outcome measures. In short, to conceptualise quality in health, it is necessary to be careful since it should not be defined in a reductive way. It is easy to perceive that the complexity that characterizes the professional practice of nursing, centred in the care, does not facilitate the understanding nor the evaluation of the quality in this area.

On the other hand, Carayon et al. [9] claimed that the measurement and validation of instruments and software's is crucial for effective operations. However, the holistic aspect of care should also be taken into consideration while carrying out this evaluation. A lack of attention to this perspective may lead to the dissatisfaction of the population, and some health professionals motivated to take care of it. The concern with quality in nurses in Mauritius has accompanied changes in society. It is necessary to consider in the assessment of care the structure (characteristics of human and technical resources); process (action to transform inputs into outputs); and result of the care provided to the users. There have been constant differentiating factors in the use of SPC, thus leading to different ways of exchanging medical information in countries all over the globe. Some countries depend on health care providers who have control over the SPC data. Further, a more comprehensive search denotes the engagement of the users to multiple kinds of health care information and a broader range of searching. Moreover, the patients can gain access to their health care information with information channels, medical journals, books, health magazines, family and acquaintances.

According to Schoville and Titler [10], when the system is successfully implemented, a high-quality emergency department medical record accurately

captures the process of management, evaluation, medical decision making as well as disposition concerning a patient encounter in emergency crisis. Furthermore, SPC system facilitates quality improvement, quality assessment, risk management practices and meaningful utilisation of software installations in emergency health care being promptly available at all times. Nowadays, the health organisations are considered as the most complex organisations along with a high degree of autonomy among multidisciplinary team. They have to cater the needs of increasingly demanding and informed users (informed not involving connoisseurs), using ever-evolving scientific technology and knowledge [11]. For the health organisation to meet the current requirements, it is fundamental to develop continuous improvement, being one of the assumptions for the certification of quality systems with well-equipped information technological systems.

While conducting research on the relationships in an organisation, the outcome, process, and structure can be associated with each other. However, it is critical to present the relationship between these variables. Figure 1 presents a model showing association among these variables.

Figure 1: The proposed model (Source: Author)

4. Ethical Considerations

This study was performed after receiving ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board. Confidentiality, IRB approval, participant reciprocity, and confidentiality procedures were used to ensure the overall method of inquiry maintained a professional approach to the study. As the participants were health care professionals and patients, their expectations were to proceed with the survey, which allowed the researcher to complete the study as designed. Everyone responsible for using data has to follow strict rules called data protection principles. They must make sure the information is:

1. Used fairly and lawfully
2. Used for limited, specifically stated purposes
3. Used in a way that is adequate, relevant and not excessive accurate
4. Kept for no longer than is necessary
5. Handled according to people's data protection rights

6. Kept safe and secure
7. Not transferred outside the European Economic Area without adequate protection

5. Research Methodology

This research is based on the pragmatism paradigm approach based on mixed methodology. This approach is used due to its significance that it does not only demonstrate the numerical data, measurements or countable numbers but also the information is expressed verbally and in words [12]. Moreover, the qualitative methodology is a contextual approach to investigate the association between paradigms of interpretive model and use it to evaluate the observation and verbal materials. On the other hand, quantitative approach relates to the application of numerical perspectives on the real life events and studies the differences between the variables acting on a particular scenario. According to Creswell [13] the principal mode of data collection in a quantitative study is close ended questionnaires which are known as affordable ways of collecting quantitative data. These instruments can be administered online or as mobile surveys having low cost and give instantaneous results with no need of printing or posting questionnaires.

Hypotheses

H₁: There is no difference between the financial cost and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

H₂: There is no difference between the infrastructure fitness and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

H₃: There is no difference between adaptability and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

6. Population and Sampling

The sampling of study population was conducted in the Republic of Mauritius. The country's estimated resident population as of 31 December 2015 was 1,220,530 inhabitants. The number of admissions in Government hospitals in 2015 was 208,241 and the number of operations performed on them was 44,427. The total number of all combined health care professionals is approximately 8700 across the entire country [14]. Therefore, designing a working framework for different participants to be recruited from both public and private health facilities provided a remarkable revelation in containing the pertinent health issues that Mauritius is facing as a country. As per the WHO definition, health professionals would be medical doctors, nursing professionals, midwifery professionals, dentists, and pharmacists. The major hospitals included in this research were Sir Seewoosagar Ramgoolam National

Hospital, AG Jeetoo Hospital, Apollo Bramwell and Victoria in Quatres Bornes. Both public and private hospitals of at least 100 beds will be considered looking at all districts. The health care executives, board members, search firm executives, and health administration managers were selected by stratified sampling 1800 participants (quantitative) and by purposive sampling method 10 respondents (qualitative). Furthermore, 434 patients attending the hospitals at that time were given questionnaires to fill them out. The targeted population for this study was professionals at the selected institutions and patients visiting the hospitals both public and private at the time of the study.

7. Data Collection

The collection of raw data was conducted in two phases; Phase 1 was a quantitative research design in which the survey questionnaire was administered. The sample size was 1800 participants; health care professionals and patients selected through stratified sampling method. Tipton et al. [15] identified that survey research is also capable of collecting data from a large sample size of participants and thus, adding validity and reliability to the research process (Table 1). The total population of patient attending the hospitals on a given day as well the health professions attendance was calculated as 1220530 [14].

Table 1: Stratification ratio

Confidence Level	Confidence Interval	Population	Sample size needed
95%	2.31	1220530	1797

The questionnaire was self-administered and each participant was given a printed copy with a cover letter explaining the aim and purpose of the research. The questionnaires were distributed to health care administrators and to the various categories of health professionals and patients visiting the hospital at that time who were on duty during the data collection period. The sample size was calculated using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) with Alpha set at 0.05; Power at 0.80, Effect Size at 0.10 and Predictors at 18. The questionnaires were 5 point Likert scale ranging from ‘strongly agree to strongly disagree’. The demographic variables were also included information about the gender, age and academic levels for the purpose of this study.

In phase 2, the interview guide was used as an outline to explore the focus questions needed to answer the research question and was developed before beginning the participant interviews. The interview guide contained questions to assist with the interview process. Qualitative phase was in form of verbatim and words quotes that is the interviews with representatives

in nine focus groups of ten participants each, recordings, coding and thematic analysis of the transcripts.

8. Validity of Instrument

The instrument was tested to identify pattern matching for internal validity. The reliability was measured in terms of Cronbach’s Alpha and ranged from 0.63 to 0.84. This reliability index was used in a study by Bonett and Wright [16], who inferred that items and dimensions of a survey are psychometrically sound at the unit level, and hospital level of assessment and can be utilised by the researchers and hospitals interesting in evaluating effectiveness of care services in health care systems. Quantitative Component presents that approximately 3000 questionnaires were given out across the nine districts of Mauritius.

Qualitative Component: Will be in the form of verbatim and words quotes that is the interviews with representatives of nine focus groups of ten participants each, recordings, coding and thematic analysis thereof of the transcripts’.

9. Variables

1. Dependent Variable:

- a) Overall Quality of Health Care (QHC): Overall quality of health care administration services rating according to the WHO.

2. Independent Variables:

- a. Financial Costs of the Services (FC): Financial costs of the services that are offered in various health care systems.
- b. Infrastructure Fitness (IF): Infrastructure fitness for the purpose of rendering quality healthcare services to the patients
- c. Adaptability (Adap): Adaptability to revolution requirements including flexibility measures that are put in place to address rising health care concerns and issues.

10. Data Analysis

The sample size was calculated using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) with Alpha set at 0.05; Power at 0.80, Effect Size at 0.10 and Predictors at 18. The questionnaires were 5-point Likert scale ranging from ‘strongly agree to disagree strongly’. The following table is representing the demographic information of the respondents. The demographic variables were also included information about the gender, age, and academic levels for the purpose of this study (Table 2).

Table 2: Demographic Statistics

Demographic Statistics

		Age 1= 25-30 years, 2=31-40 years; 3=41-50 years)	Gender	Educational Level (1= 5 years, 2=7 years; 3=10 years)
N	Valid	1750	1750	1750
	Missing	50	50	50
Mean		2.93	2.68	1.27
Median		2.00	2.00	2.00
Mode		2	2	2
Std. Deviation		5.211	1.196	10.035
Variance		10.258	1.955	5.692

In phase 2, five major categories of interview questions were developed. Within these five major categories, three main questions were described as descriptive, structural, and contrast questions, which used to create initial interview questions and additional questions asked throughout the interviews to ensure adequate data were obtained.

11. Credibility, Dependability, Confirmability, & Transferability

The study was narrowed to four large hospitals due to the limitation to resources both in time and money needed to administer the survey in a more widely dispersed geographical area. Limiting of the participants to Sir Seewoosagar Ramgoolam National Hospital, AG Jeetoo Hospital, Apollo Bramwell and Victoria in Quatres Bornes was not seen as an issue because the results were true for the hospital selected at the time. Therefore, it is believed that transferability of the findings may be possible. The directories included names of health care administrators and their related titles, health care administration certifications, demographics, and affiliated health care systems. All nine health care executives included in the study were from these sources except for one. This health care executive participant was selected due to his affiliation with a very large integrated health care system in one of the hospitals used. The two search firm executives were selected from the state directories as well.

10. Reliability

Cronbach's alpha is the most reliable measure of the reliability of the survey instrument, also called inter-rater reliability or internal consistency rating. This statistical measure is commonly used in multiple Likert or survey questionnaire to form a scale. This scale functions on the basis of the survey structured response framework, ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree". In this research, this scale is used to measure and

understand whether the questions included in the survey are all reliable and have the similar latent variables (Table 3 & 4). This scale was used on a sample of 1800 but completely valid were 1750 questionnaires that depicted an alpha value of 0.632. This shows that our survey questionnaire has a high internal reliability.

Table 3: Case Processing Summary

		N	percent
Cases	Valid	1750	97.22
	Excluded ^a	50	0.28
	Total	1800	100.0

a. List-wise deletion based on all variables in the procedure

Table 4: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.632	67

10. Results

Phase 1A - Quantitative Research

The acquired quantitative data was carefully analysed and presented in terms of descriptive and inferential statistics. Around 1811 questionnaires were retrieved and the received data was collected and fed into SPSS to drive results starting by generating random numbers. Statistical software 20.0 was used to perform statistical analysis on the data collected through survey. Descriptive statistics for the demo-graphic characteristics of the respondents and the items in the survey were first analysed. T-test was performed and then conducted to compare the mean differences between the dimensions of theses questionnaire and positive responses' score. One-way ANOVA examined the mean differences between the responses and the rate of responses between the selected hospitals. Pearson correlation was conducted to examine the relation between independent variables with a mean percentage reporting a positive score as the dependent variable.

QHC in Comparison with FC

H1: There is no difference between the financial cost and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

Table 5: Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair	QHC	3.00	1750	0.43	0.01
1	FC	2.99	1750	0.47	0.01

In the Paired Samples Statistics Box, the mean for the QHC is 3.00. The mean for the FC is 2.99. The standard deviation for the QHC is 0.43 and for the FC, also 0.47. The number of participants in the sample (N) was 1750 (Table 5).

Table 6: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences				t	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	95 percent Confidence Interval of the Difference			
			Lower	Upper		
QHC - FC	0.01	0.64	-0.02	0.03	0.16	0.87

Because of this, we can conclude that there is a statistically significant difference between the QHC and FC. The paired samples statistics box revealed that the mean number for organisational fitness compliance was greater than the Mean for the quality of health care (Table 6). Therefore, it can be stated that there is no statistical difference between financial cost and quality of health care.

QHC in Comparison with IF

H₂: There is no difference between the infrastructure fitness and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

Table 7: Paired Samples Statistics

Pair	QHC	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
1	IF	2.99	1750	0.47	0.01

In the Paired Samples Statistics Box, the mean for the QHC is 3.00. The mean for the IF is 2.99. The standard deviation for the QHC is 0.43 and for the IF, 0.47. The number of participants in the sample (N) was 1750 (Table 7).

Taking into account the above-mentioned figures, it can be concluded that there is a statistically significant difference between the QHC and IF. Since the paired samples statistics box revealed that, the mean number for compliance was less than the Mean for the quality of health care (Table 8). Therefore, it can be concluded that participants who showed preference for infrastructure fitness principally experience better quality of care.

Table 8: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
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	Mean	Std. Deviation	95 percent Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	Sig.
			Lower	Upper		
QHC - IF	0.01	0.63	-0.03	0.04	0.25	0.05

QHC in Comparison with Adap

H₃: There is no difference between adaptability and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

Table 9: Paired Samples Statistics

Pair	QHC	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
1	Adap	3.00	1750	0.54	0.01

In the Paired Samples Statistics Box, the mean for the QHC is 3.00. The mean for the Adap is 3.00. The standard deviation for the QHC is 0.43 and for the Adap, 0.54. The number of participants in the sample (N) was 1750 (Table 9).

Table 10: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences				t	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	95 percent Confidence Interval of the Difference			
			Lower	Upper		
QHC - Adap	-0.01	0.69	-0.04	0.03	-0.04	0.03

According to the results obtained, it can be affirmed that there is a statistically significant difference between the QHC and Adaptability. Since the paired samples statistics box revealed that, the mean number for ISO compliance was less than the Mean for the quality of health care (Table 10). Therefore, the researcher can conclude that participants who showed preference for adaptability principally experience better quality of care.

Phase 1B - Application of Statistical Process Control Analysis

The evaluation of the model through statistical process control analysis is a systematic approach. Every step is interlinked with the previous step and utilising more sophisticated statistical method. In the first step, the researchers conducted exploratory factor analysis (EFA)

to point out as well as isolate the variables which were not loaded potentially into the intended factors. In the second step, the researchers conducted a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to assess whether or not the variable reflects the significant factor as intended.

Furthermore, the good model fit was also presented via a non-significant p-value ($p > 0.05$), by a “short root mean square error of approximation”, i.e. RMSEA < 0.08 . It was indicated by the high comparative fit index (CFI), i.e. approximately 1.00. If the data set and the model are not potentially different, this indicates that there is a good model fit involved in the research. Moreover, to identify potential difference between SEM and CFA, analysis was conducted among the groups of responders

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Around 14 out of 18 variables presented the factor loading of more than 0.30 on their intended factor. On the other hand, the process variables related to the efficiency of health care administration and employees did not load considerably at either factors, whereas the two outcome variables associated with the competence of health care administration did not load significantly onto their intended factors. Table 11 presents the EFA among the variables.

Table 11: Results of Exploratory Factor Analysis

Factors	Factor 1 Structure	Factor 2 Process	Factor 3 Outcome
Variables			
A1	0.76	-0.00	-0.04
A2	0.86	-0.20	-0.13
A3	0.58	0.10	0.01
A4	0.57	-0.00	0.15
A5	0.57	0.09	0.10
A6	0.70	0.04	-0.01
B1	0.15	0.42	-0.10
B2	0.29	0.29	-0.03
B3	0.09	0.27	0.04
B4	-0.07	0.90	-0.02
B5	0.02	0.83	-0.03
B6	-0.05	0.81	0.05
C1	0.34	0.04	0.49
C2	0.11	0.08	0.77
C3	-0.02	-0.08	0.99
C4	-0.03	0.08	0.72

Factors	Factor 1 Structure	Factor 2 Process	Factor 3 Outcome
C5	0.44	0.18	0.15
C6	0.42	0.14	0.06

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

The initial CFA related to 14 variables presented that the expected structure was not reflected by the variable A2, indicating the variance of 27%. However, a total of 13 variables (excluding A2) presented adequate reflection of all variables onto their intended factors. The p value was found to be < 0.01 , thus indicating that the correlation between factors was significantly less than one (95% confidence interval). These results indicated a good construct validity among the variables, as mentioned in Table 12.

Table 12: Results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis.

Factor	Variable	Loading	Standard error	
Structure	A1	0.88**	0.06	
	A3	0.78**	0.07	
	A4	0.98**	0.08	
	A5	1.19**	0.07	
	A6	1.06**	0.07	
	Process	B1	0.59**	0.07
B4		1.14**	0.06	
B5		1.21**	0.06	
B6		1.04**	0.07	
Outcome		C1	1.12**	0.07
		C2	1.38**	0.07
	C3	1.17**	0.08	
	C4	0.96**	0.08	

**p < 0.01

Model is a reasonable representation of the data:
 $\chi^2 (59) = 73.7$,
 $p = 0.09$,
 RMSEA = 0.00, and
 CFI = 1.00

95% Confidence intervals for bivariate factor correlations:

- Structure – Process: 0.66–0.80
- Structure – Outcome: 0.67–0.83
- Process – Outcome: 0.54–0.74

Reliability

The reliability was found to be higher for all almost factors, i.e. 0.80. This reliability score was appropriate

indicating good extracted variance for the process, i.e. 0.52, while the outcome was found to be 0.58. Furthermore, the mediocre for structure was indicated as 0.43. These measures of model fit affirmed that the data set was reasonably presented by the questionnaire, i.e. CFI = 1.00, RMSEA < 0.08, and $p > 0.05$.

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

In accordance with the proposed model, the structural model was appropriate ($p = 0.09$). Therefore, it can be affirmed that the data set and model can differ from each other. The process and structure of health care organisation are potentially interlinked with each other, i.e. 0.72 and 0.60, respectively. Therefore, the overall relation between outcome and structure was potentially strong including the path via process, i.e. 0.75. The overall variation in outcome was found to be 58 % between the process and structure.

Figure 2: Result of Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

All relationships are significant ($p < 0.05$).

The model is a reasonable representation of the data:

$\chi^2 (59) = 73.7$

$p = 0.095$

RMSEA = 0.000

CFI = 1.00

Phase 2: Qualitative Analysis

The second phase of this research is based on interview-based qualitative research methodology. A brief, informal and positive introduction was given to the participants included in the research. The anonymity of interviewed and the confidentiality of responses was ensured. The themes generated by separating repetitive triads are later analysed through content analysis, where in, the following step were undertaken to de-construct themes in accordance with the collected data (Chart 1);

Chart 1: Phase 2; Qualitative method

Initially, the participants tended to digress and in some instances hesitated as if they were not sure what was being asked. After the first two interviews, changes were made to the original questions. The changes in the questions made a significant impact on the participants' understanding of the questions, thus increasing the amount and quality of the data obtained, as participants were able to relate very well to the revised questions, and their answers were comprehensive. Specifically, instead of asking about areas of administration the questions were changed to ask about "roles and responsibilities," and in addition to asking about "the most pressing and stressful administrative issues" the questions were changed to ask about "what issues kept them awake at night" and, instead of asking about the "context of these administrative issues" questions were asked about what the "environment was like when dealing with these administrative issues." Early participants commented on what health administration higher education programs should teach. Therefore, a question was added to subsequent interviews that asked this question.

The interview sessions lasted for nearly half an hour and all respondents were given open ended. The researcher has also probed small questions in between the main questions in order to extract more information out of respondents. The interview was conducted in a friendly environment and the researcher was concerned not to influence the responses, put himself or herself in a posture of listener, and seek to maintain a good and stimulating environment. The researcher also extracted information while the respondents were answering the questions any observation by the way the respondents were answering, their gestures and through their non-verbal or body language. In this regard, Creswell [13]

ratifies the use of a tape recorder, because it allows the interviewer to focus on the talk and record the interviewee's non-verbal gestures during the interview.

One of the respondents reported that there are different uses of information technology (IT) and related softwares based on situation and places. He said that:

"The innovative use of health care technology would be different in different place and different situation. It does not have any standard definition. Different country has different infrastructure according to their economic condition, manpower and geographical structure...If anybody uses ISO for medical care whether it is store-forward or real time; in that sense we are doing telemedicine in Mauritius" (Participant no. 1).

Furthermore, while asking a respondent if he thinks that the development of standards of practices in IT in relation to the operations of health care systems will relieve the country from its pending health care problems? One of the administrative managers replied as; *"We just have started to work in this field and we have plan about SPC but it is true that, we don't have enough workforce yet regarding telemedicine and e-health. Awareness about this matter is very much important among the health personnel as well as the patients. The private health sector can also take initiatives concerning this issue, as 60 percent of patients take health care services from private clinics and hospitals in Mauritius"* (Participant no. 4).

In addition, the researcher asked a participant about the requirements for improvement in the health administration residency programmes. In addition, participants were asked whether they thought the "role was greater than it was 20 years ago" as this theme began to emerge from the early participants. Therefore, this question was added to subsequent interviews to explore this area, as it seemed to allow the participants to expand on their roles and responsibilities, which provided additional data related to the study. Moreover, the participants were also inquired about the effectivity of health care services in accordance with the current standards of information technology. One of the participant responded that: *"I believe that the introduction of new technologies, such as SPC can improve the delivery and operations of health care services in a relatively shorter tie as well as with reduced cost"* (Participant no. 5).

11. Discussion

The results revealed a significant number of evidences to reveal the importance of integrating information technology services into the field of health care. In both of the research methodologies, it has been indicated that the use of IT in organisational operations has provide productive results with improved QHC services. The combination of quantitative and qualitative data made

some important revelations to the study. The researcher has high confidence in the research data and therefore states that what respondents and participants to the study have revealed is representative of the entire population in the research. According to the results, patients' participants depicted that there is wide range of IT services that can be utilised to improve the QHC in the organisation. These results are consistent with the findings of Schembri who assessed the use of information technology and permanent and qualified monitoring of clients or patients as an important aspect of quality care [17]. The adoption of this SPC model can represent an output not only of low cost but, mainly, of higher resolution. As a condition of citizenship, the idea of health ensures more and better years of life, points to certain specificities of health workers. The commitments of these agents with an expanded conception of health transcend the sectoral and tend to diversify their fields of practice.

Referring to the results obtained regarding the relationship between infrastructure and quality of health care, it has been observed that the mean number for compliance was less than the mean for the quality of health care. This means that the health care practitioners are supposed to provide a better quality of care in improved infrastructure. Hence, there is a statistically significant difference between the QHC and IF.

As far as the relationship between financial cost and quality of health care, the results have revealed that there is no statistically significant difference between the QHC and financial cost. Moreover, the relationship between QHC and adaptability was also assessed. The results indicated that participants who showed preference for adaptability principally experience better QHC. Therefore, it was stated that there is a statistically significant difference between the QHC and adaptability.

Furthermore, the results of SEM and CFA indicated that the relation between outcomes, processes, and structures is potential to indicate the flow of administration in the health care organisation with respect to the quality system. It has been observed that almost all variables indicated adequate reflection onto their intended factors. Moreover, the p value of < 0.01 indicated that the correlation between factors was significantly less than one (95% confidence interval). Finally, the reliability of 0.8 presented a good extracted variance for the process for all almost factors.

A research by Bork-Hüffer indicated that health care facilities have downplayed the importance of patient care and this had negatively affected the image of health care administrations [18]. It is further notified from the results that health care environment in Mauritius when competition has become quite keen, patient care and satisfaction have become the prime concerns of each and every health care facility. In the contemporary time

health care administrations are increasingly, becoming clients' focused. Therefore, it is also imperative to consider whether the health care services are affordable for the service users. The inefficiency and institutional weakness of health organisations can have their causes in administrative devaluation or lack of managerial skills. Hence, the administrative dilemmas associated with political, financial and cultural problems coexist. Therefore, one should not be making propositions of a managerial change in these organisations as if they were magical solutions capable of solving everything.

One of the critical characteristics of these administrations would be the absence of clearly defined objectives to guide management action. This makes hospital organisations move by punctual actions. In addition, because of the lack of a reference for the organisation's management, goal substitution occurs [3]. In this case, the organisation tends to institute survival as its primary mission. Nowadays, the adoption of limiting measures or even prerequisites for the fulfilment of management positions is making it difficult for those individuals without previous training in health administration. The other line of propositions involves the decentralisation cited by Kalendzhyan one of the aspects that have drawn attention to the new discussions about hospital management and that of organisations, in general, is the need for decentralisation in decision making [3, 6]. Authors mention that one of the ways an organisation works with greater or less efficiency would be to decentralise decision-making power, making them more autonomous in management and administrative ability. In other words, it is not enough for the manager to have the interest and the capacity to make decisions; it is indispensable that he has the authority to decide.

However, Bork-Hüffer further instigated that the era of empiricism in hospital management has its days counted [18]. Administrative and financial tools are increasingly needed. The management tool that will be of greater utility for the public or private administration will be sought, both in financial and administrative planning. This new paradigm tends to demand more relevant information related to the FC of activities, processes, products and patients. These changes require greater expenses with training, technological development, engineering, marketing and improvement in the quality of patient service delivery. The concept of hospital administration is changed; the way of managing is changed. Managers are more receptive to transformations. Perceptions about the processes of strategic change in a hospital are very varied, which is highly explicable and understandable because of its complexity. Nevertheless, on the other hand, we know that change today is of great importance to organisations, even as a means of their survival and sustainability in a

future scenario, a fact that hospitals and their leaders are finding difficulty in managing.

It is significant to note that the technological advances are geometric and the prices charged by Mauritian hospitals are increasing. Technology is a determining factor for rising health costs. In the case of Mauritian hospitals, however, there is another crucial problem; administration. According to Kearney-Nunnery, only 1 percent of Mauritian hospitals had a professional management, which meant a qualified hospital administrator who had a dynamic and futuristic vision [19]. Most at that time had an administrative-financial direction occupied by doctors who did not have the technical preparation to run a company of such administrative complexity. Schembri further argued that the costs of Mauritian hospitals were poorly worked out [17]. In fact, few hospital administrations were concerned about costs. The vast majority lived by increasing their price list regardless of the actual analysis of their hospital cost. Jones-Farmer et al. explained at the time that one of the difficulties of the change in Mauritian hospitals was due to immobility [3]. Immobility means not changing the modus operandi in order not to create new demands or to remain quiet in its corner as a well-established strategy of territorial defence.

The health area is now looking for industry and production engineering, examples of how to optimise hospital management through the improvement of its processes and the use of management tools. The change process requires the manager to have a horizontal view of the organisation, general knowledge and leadership on the most varied professional areas. Unfortunately, managerial training that is not always adequate for managers especially in public health contributes to the lack of vision of these hospitals affect overall QHC. Administrative and financial tools are increasingly needed [17]. Further, the hospital organisations, particularly public ones, need well-formed guidance that will contribute to their maturation as companies. It is significant to consider that physicians are primarily concerned with care and service delivery, according to the needs of each case regardless of FC, and if we consider that the manager thinks primarily of the financial balance of the organisation and the patient's final FC, we will be adding the ingredient of tension between two sets of values [10].

In this way, we will be creating a conflict of objectives, that is, the money versus services dilemma [8]. As if foreseeing these dilemmas, past researchers suggest that there was a need to establish a system of control of care activities under the responsibility of the hospital administration, seeking to fill a system of medical self-regulation and not simply as a bureaucratic tool. According to Goldschmidt et al. this debate probably

inserts the first dilemmas of modern medicine in relation to the rationalisation of intra-hospital costs, where on the one hand is the administrator, who establishes the accounting procedures, intending to reduce as much as possible the expenses with patients who were able to pay the bills and waited for the formal rules [20]. At the other end, there is medical personnel who perform procedures and who judge the services for the clinical results achieved and not for their costs.

12. Conclusion

The results revealed that the impacts of changes in both supply and demand for health services, taking into account the stochastic nature of the same, is being a tool capable of assisting decision-makers in the development and improvement of Ministry of Health planning in Mauritius. The technological advances are geometric and the prices charged by Mauritian hospitals are increasing. In the case of Mauritian hospitals, however, there is another crucial problem; administration that is only 1 percent of Mauritian hospitals had a professional management, which meant a qualified hospital administrator who had a dynamic and futuristic vision. Most at that time had an administrative-financial direction occupied by doctors who did not have the technical preparation to run a company of such administrative complexity. In addition, the costs of Mauritian hospitals were poorly worked out. In fact, few hospital administrations were concerned about costs. The vast majority lived by increasing their price list regardless of the actual analysis of their hospital cost.

The health area is now looking for industry and production engineering, examples of how to optimise hospital management through the improvement of its processes and the use of management tools. The change process requires the manager to have a horizontal view of the organisation, general knowledge and leadership on the most varied professional areas. Unfortunately, managerial training that is not always adequate for managers especially in public health contributes to the lack of vision of these hospitals as a company. Administrative and financial tools are increasingly needed. Further, the hospital organisations, particularly public ones, need well-formed guidance that will contribute to their maturation as companies. The results obtained from this research are found to be consistent with other researches, which highlighted the importance of advanced softwares and their significance in the health care organisations. However, this research has few limitations. This study used quantitative method only as mixed methodology that would have provided the quantitative input by the participants as well. Future research should use longitudinal data to further test these results. Second, the measures for the health care outcomes in this paper are self-reported, so future

research may use objective measures to validate the proposed SPC implementation.

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